

ANALYSIS OF LABOR PROTECTION IN THE NEW EDITION OF THE LABOR CODE

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Abstract. *Labor protection is a crucial component of the system for managing the safety and health of employees regulated by the Labor Code, as well as a significant aspect of labor legislation.*

Keywords: *labor protection, Requirements for labor protection, Employer, Employee.*

This Code regulates individual labor relations and the social relations directly related to them by ensuring a balance of interests among employees, employers, and the state, while facilitating their coordination. [1]

Labor protection is an integral part of labor relations and plays a key role in ensuring the health and safety of workers. The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the basis for creating an effective labor protection system that defines the rights and obligations of the parties. However, in order to achieve high results by establishing performance indicators, it is necessary to constantly improve legislation and raise the ethical culture of employers and employees on the importance of compliance with labor protection standards.

The main objectives of the Labor Code are:

establishment of state guarantees of labor rights and freedoms of employees, including the right to work, free choice of work, fair and safe working conditions, protection from unemployment;

ensuring the implementation of the rights of employers in the field of selection, placement and organization of an effective labor process;

encouragement and development of social partnership in the field of labor;

ensuring the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of employees and employers;

support for the effective functioning of the labor market. [1]

Forced labor is prohibited by the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Forced labor means any work or service required from an individual under threat of punishment, for the performance of which this person does not voluntarily offer his services. Punishment means the use or threat of application to this person of any measures of material, physical or moral influence forcing him to perform work without his voluntary consent. [1]

Other legal documents on labor include collective agreements, collective contracts, internal documents adopted by the employer in accordance with an agreement with the trade union committee, internal documents, including individual legal documents adopted by the employer within the limits of its authority.

The employee has the following rights to:

a workplace that meets labor protection requirements;

working conditions that meet safety and hygiene requirements;

receiving complete and reliable information about working conditions and labor protection requirements at the workplace.

One of the main responsibilities of the employee is to comply with labor protection requirements, technological discipline, labor safety rules and industrial sanitation, and the employer's obligation to ensure safety and working conditions in accordance with regulatory labor protection requirements is approved by the Labor Code.

Improvement of working conditions and labor protection for women, disabled people and persons under eighteen years of age is reflected in the content and structure of the Collective Agreement. It is envisaged that collective agreements must include information on wages, working conditions and labor protection, work and rest schedule, and health protection of production workers.

In cases where training, knowledge and skills in the field of labor protection have not been completed and (or) the employee has not used personal and (or) collective protective equipment that must be used in accordance with labor legislation or labor protection. The rules for dismissing an employee are strictly defined.

Labor protection is a system of legal, socio-economic, organizational, technical, sanitary and hygienic, medical and preventive, rehabilitation measures and means that ensure the safety, life and health of a person, and the preservation of working capacity in the process of work. [2]

Occupational safety requirements:

Employers are required to provide working conditions that meet safety and hygiene requirements.

Occupational safety requirements are defined by this Code, other legal documents, as well as regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation of occupational safety issues.

Occupational safety requirements define the rules, procedures and criteria aimed at protecting the life and health of the employee during work.

Occupational safety requirements during the design, construction (reconstruction) of facilities, their operation, construction of machines, mechanisms and other equipment, development of technological processes, organization of production and labor, as well as other types of legal activities must be followed by persons.

Personal and collective protective equipment for workers must comply with occupational safety requirements and have a certificate of conformity.

The procedure for developing, approving and amending regulatory documents containing occupational safety requirements and occupational safety rules is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account proposals from the Republican Tripartite Commission on Social and Labor Issues. [2]

The main role of occupational safety and health is to create a safe and healthy working environment for workers, which directly affects their productivity and overall well-being. The Labor Code defines the rights and obligations of employees and employers, establishes standards aimed at preventing occupational diseases and accidents at work.

Rights and obligations of an employee in the field of labor protection:

An employee has the following rights:

to have a workplace in accordance with the requirements of regulatory legal documents and labor protection rules;

to receive information from the employer on working conditions, including the risk of contracting occupational and other diseases, benefits and compensation that must be provided to him in connection with this, as well as on personal and collective protective equipment;

to be provided with personal protective equipment at the expense of the employer in accordance with established labor protection standards and requirements;

to have compulsory state social insurance against accidents at work and occupational diseases in the manner prescribed by law;

in the event of a danger to life and health due to violation of labor protection requirements - refusal to perform work until such danger is eliminated;

to demand an inspection of the conditions and labor protection at his workplace by the body exercising state control and verification of compliance with labor protection requirements;

to get training in safe work practices and techniques at the expense of the employer;

to receive benefits and compensations established by law;

to receive compensation by the employer for harm caused to the life or health of the employee due to the fact that he/she became disabled at work, suffered an occupational disease or other harm to health in connection with the performance of his/her work duties;

to participate personally or participate through his/her representatives in the consideration of issues related to ensuring safe working conditions at their workplace, in the investigation of an accident or occupational disease that occurred to them;

to undergo a medical examination in accordance with medical recommendations while maintaining the place of work (position) and average salary;

to receive training and retraining at the expense of the employer in the event of dismissal due to violation of labor protection requirements.

The employee may also have other rights in accordance with the law.

Employee is obliged:

to comply with the requirements of regulatory legal documents and labor protection rules;

to use correctly the personal protective equipment;

to undergo labor protection training, study and improve skills in labor protection issues;

to undergo mandatory medical examinations;

to immediately inform the employer of any situation that directly threatens the life and health of people, as well as of any accident that occurred during the work or process related to it.

The employee may also have other responsibilities in accordance with the law.

Guarantees of conditions that meet labor protection requirements:

The state guarantees the protection of the right of employees to work in conditions that meet labor protection requirements.

Working conditions stipulated by the employment contract must comply with labor protection requirements.

If the employer's activities are suspended due to violation of labor protection requirements, the employee's workplace (position) and average earnings are retained. In this case, the employee may be transferred by the employer to another job with his consent with the receipt of payment for the work he performs, but not less than the average salary at the previous place of work.

In the event of an employee's refusal to perform work in the presence of a danger to his life and health, the employer is obliged to provide the employee with other work until such danger is eliminated.

If it is impossible to employ the employee in another job for objective reasons, the employer shall pay compensation for the employee's downtime until the danger to his life and health is eliminated in accordance with Part Two of Article 266 of this Code.

If the employee is not provided with personal and collective protective equipment in accordance with the established standards, the employer has no right to require the employee to perform his work duties, in connection with which he is obliged to pay remuneration in accordance with Part Two of Article 266 of this Code.

An employee's refusal to perform work in harmful and (or) hazardous working conditions not provided for by the employment contract, in the event of a danger to his life and health due to a violation of labor protection requirements, does not entail bringing him to disciplinary responsibility.

In the event of harm to the life and health of an employee in connection with the performance of his work duties, compensation for this harm is carried out in accordance with the legislation.

In order to prevent and eliminate violations of labor protection requirements, the state ensures the organization and implementation of state control and verification of compliance with these requirements, and determines the liability of the employer and its officials for violation of these requirements.

Rights and obligations of the employer in the field of labor protection

The employer has the following rights:

to require employees to comply with standards, rules and instructions on labor protection and safe work;

to conduct a medical examination of employees to check the state of intoxication with alcoholic beverages, narcotics or toxic substances;

to appeal to a higher authority or official or directly to the court decisions of bodies implementing state control and verification of compliance with labor protection requirements, actions (inaction) of their officials;

to take measures to remunerate and provide material incentives to employees for compliance with labor protection requirements;

to make disciplinary action against employees guilty of violating labor protection requirements.

The employer may also have other rights in accordance with the law.

Employer is obliged:

to ensure that working conditions at each workplace comply with occupational safety requirements;

to create an occupational safety management system and ensure its functioning;

to ensure the safety of employees during the operation of buildings, structures, equipment, during technological processes, as well as during the use of raw materials and materials in production, during the performance of work and the provision of services;

to monitor the state of working conditions at workplaces, especially harmful production factors and hazardous production factors;

to inform employees in a timely manner about working conditions, including the risk of occupational and other diseases, the state of labor protection at specific workplaces and in production, as well as the benefits and compensations that should be provided to them in this regard, and personal and collective protective equipment;

to organize the labor protection service and the road safety service in accordance with the established norms;

to provide employees with milk, therapeutic and preventive food, carbonated saline water, personal protective and hygiene products, as well as collective protective equipment;

to ensure the provision of sanitary, household and medical services to employees in accordance with legislative acts, as well as labor protection rules;

to ensure that employees undergo labor protection instruction, training, retraining, advanced training and testing of their knowledge on labor protection issues;

not to employ employees who have not undergone training, instruction and knowledge testing on labor protection;

to conduct certification of workplaces where employees working in harmful, dangerous and other working conditions are granted benefits and compensations, are granted the right to retire on preferential terms, and are occupied by persons with disabilities in accordance with the procedure established by law;

to organize initial (upon entry into employment) and periodic (during employment) mandatory medical examinations;

to provide the bodies exercising state control and inspection over compliance with labor protection requirements, as well as trade unions and other representative bodies of employees with the information and materials necessary for control, inspection and monitoring of the state of labor protection, investigation of accidents at work and occupational diseases;

to prevent accidents, take measures to preserve the life and health of employees in the event of such incidents, including providing first aid to victims;

to timely execute instructions of bodies exercising state control and inspection over compliance with labor protection requirements and timely consider submissions of trade unions and other representative bodies of employees;

to ensure compulsory state social insurance of employees against industrial accidents and occupational diseases, as well as compulsory insurance of the employer's civil liability;

to carry out an investigation into industrial accidents and occupational diseases, as well as keep records of them.

The employer may also have other obligations in accordance with the legislation. The structure of the buildings (structures) in which workplaces are located must correspond to their established functional purpose and the requirements for labor safety and labor protection.

Instruction and training of employees on labor protection:

The employer must provide all new employees, as well as employees transferred to other jobs, with instructions on labor protection, organize training on safe methods and techniques of performing work, and assistance to victims of industrial accidents.

For employees entering high-risk production or work requiring professional selection, initial training on performing work using safe methods and techniques, occupational safety training for one month, an exam, and then mandatory periodic certification on labor protection issues are carried out.

Employees of organizations, including their managers, must be trained, instructed, and tested on labor protection by the bodies implementing state management of labor protection in accordance with the procedure and within the time limits established for the profession and types of work of these employees and managers.

The employer must dismiss persons who have not undergone training, instruction, and testing on labor protection in accordance with the established procedure.

Employees who perform their labor activities in unfavorable working conditions and unfavorable natural and climatic conditions are provided with additional guarantees regarding labor protection, working hours, vacations, remuneration, and other working conditions.

Conclusion: The Labor Code regulates individual labor relations and social relations directly related to them. The Labor Code establishes standards aimed at preventing occupational diseases and accidents at work, the rights and obligations of employees and employers. Constant analysis of the improvement of the labor protection and safety system requires adaptation to changes in working conditions and technologies. Thus, labor protection and safety create the basis for a stable and prosperous business, taking into account the interests of all parties.

REFERENCES

1. Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan 30.04.2023.
2. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-6257288>